

EVOLUTIONARY CHANGES IN THE INCIDENCE OF CERTAIN DISEASES AMONG THE POPULATION OF URGUT DISTRICT

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Abstract. This article analyzes the dynamics of major disease groups based on statistical data from 2000–2023. In recent years, a sharp increase in anemia and gastrointestinal diseases, as well as a decrease in some other diseases, has been particularly emphasized..

Keywords: morbidity, Urgut district, anemia, gastrointestinal diseases, health statistics.

Introduction. The relationship between environmental pollution and public health is one of the most pressing issues in modern environmental epidemiology. Numerous studies have shown that environmental factors have a direct impact on the population’s morbidity level [1]. In particular, air pollution accounts for nearly 30% of respiratory diseases [2].

The types and numbers of diseases observed in the district have changed over time. Under the influence of natural and anthropogenic factors, natural components such as soil, water, and air have been polluted by various wastes, which in turn has led to the emergence and dynamic change of several diseases. In the region, cancer, certain infectious diseases, cardiovascular disorders, nervous system diseases, anemia, gastrointestinal disorders, viral hepatitis, kidney stones, and similar diseases are the most common. Below, we will discuss these diseases and their changes over the years.

Table-1

Incidence of Certain Disease Groups among the District Population (per 100,000 people)

Year	Cancer	Certain infectious and parasitic diseases	Cardiovascular diseases	Nervous system disorders
2005	40,8	461,0	205,1	517,2
2010	64,5	627,8	319,5	565,0
2015	114,8	702,3	389,0	630,2
2020	262,5	880,3	126,0	623,4
2023	57,5	1121,5	45,3	771,5

Table compiled by the author based on data from the Samarkand Regional Health Department.

According to oncologists, the increase in cancer cases is largely associated with air pollution, particularly with the presence of harmful and carcinogenic substances. Industrial emissions, vehicle exhaust gases, and tobacco smoke are considered the main factors. Moreover, internal carcinogens formed within the human body also contribute to disease development. Environmentally unfavorable conditions and the consumption of contaminated food products also play a significant role.

As shown in the table, in 2000 the incidence rate was 45.1 per 100,000 population. The highest rate was recorded in 2020, reaching 262.5 per 100,000, but by 2023 it had decreased significantly to 57.5 per 100,000.

Picture 1. Incidence of certain disease groups among the district population (per 100,000 people). Compiled by the author based on data from the Samarkand Regional Health Department.

Among the most prevalent diseases in the district are infectious and parasitic diseases. Their spread is mainly associated with socio-economic factors. Population density plays a crucial role in the spread of such diseases. In large settlements with high population density, extensive use of public transport, and crowded places such as parks, theaters, and stadiums, the spread of infections like hepatitis A and influenza is often linked to human factors.

In Urgut district, there are 499 people per square kilometer. Demographers consider a density of 50 people per km² to be high. As the population has increased, the incidence of these diseases has also grown over the years. In 2005, there were 461 cases per 100,000 people, increasing to 627.8 in 2010, 702.3 in

2015, 880.3 in 2020, and 1121.5 in 2023. The data indicate a significant rise in these diseases over the past three years.

The increase in cardiovascular diseases in Urgut district is related to several factors, including socio-economic problems such as employment levels, deteriorating environmental conditions, especially air and water pollution, and the effects of chemicals used in agriculture. The rate of cardiovascular diseases per 100,000 people increased after 2005. In that year, 205.1 per 100,000 were affected, rising to 319.5 in 2010 and 389.0 in 2015. However, this rate decreased to 126.0 in 2020 and further to 45.3 in 2023. This indicates a decline in cardiovascular disease cases in recent years.

In the studied region, the incidence of nervous system disorders did not change drastically over the years but showed a general upward trend. In 2005, there were 517.2 cases per 100,000 people, increasing to 565.0 in 2010 and 630.2 in 2015. By 2020, the rate slightly decreased to 623.4 but rose again in 2023 to 771.5 per 100,000. This represents a 24% increase compared to the previous five-year period.

Anemia is one of the most common diseases among the district population. The rate of anemia has varied over the years but generally increased with population growth. In 2005, there were 3,760.3 cases per 100,000 people, increasing to 4,253.4 in 2010 and 4,752.5 in 2015. In 2020, the rate dropped to 3,596.6 but rose again in 2023, showing a sharp increase in the past three years.

Conclusion. The results of the study show that environmental pollution in Urgut district has a direct impact on public health. The incidence of cancer, infectious, cardiovascular, nervous system, and anemia diseases has changed differently over the years. In recent years, cancer and cardiovascular diseases have decreased, while infectious, nervous, and anemia cases have increased. These changes are mainly due to environmental degradation, population density, and socio-economic factors. Therefore, it is essential to create a healthier ecological environment and strengthen preventive measures.

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